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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF FLOATING LIPID
BEADS OF RUPATADINE FOR THE ENHANCED
BIOAVAILABILITY AND ITS PHARMACOKINETIC
APPLICATIONS****Dr.N.Sandeepthi¹, Nellutla Jhancy Laxmi^{2*}, Kummari Eshwaramma**¹Associate Professor, Vignan Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Deshmukhi village,
Yadadri bhuvanagiri Dist²Associate Professor, Omega College of Pharmacy, Edulabad, Hyderabad, Ghatkesar,
Telangana 501301**Abstract:**

The development of oral drug delivery systems for poorly soluble basic drugs is problematic because of their pH dependent solubility. Poorly water soluble basic drugs are very sensitive to pH changes, and following oral administration and dissolution in the acidic stomach environment, they tend to precipitate upon gastric emptying to higher pH medium in the intestine, leading to compromised or erratic oral bioavailability. Rupatadine is a second-generation antihistamine, long-acting histamine antagonist, with selective peripheral H1-receptor antagonist activity. Some of the metabolites (desloratadine and its hydroxylated metabolites) retain an antihistaminic activity and may partially contribute to the overall efficacy of the drug. This compound belongs to the class of organic compounds known as benzo-cyclo-hepta-pyridines. These are aromatic compounds containing a benzene ring and a pyridine ring fused to a seven membered carbocycle. In vitro studies with rupatadine at high concentration have shown an inhibition of the degranulation of mast cells induced by immunological and non-immunological stimuli as well in human mast cells and monocytes as the release of cytokines, particularly of the TNF.

Keywords: *Rupatadine, H1 receptor antagonist, benzo-cyclo-hepta-pyridines, TNF***Corresponding author:****Nellutla Jhancy Laxmi ,**

Associate Professor,

Omega College of Pharmacy,

Edulabad, Hyderabad, Ghatkesar,

Telangana 501301

Email id: nellutla.jhancy@gmail.com

QR code

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The development of oral drug delivery systems for poorly soluble basic drugs is problematic because of their pH dependent solubility. Poorly water soluble basic drugs are very sensitive to pH changes, and following oral administration and dissolution in the acidic stomach environment, they tend to precipitate upon gastric emptying to higher pH medium in the intestine, leading to compromised or erratic oral bioavailability [1,2].

Rupatadine is a second-generation antihistamine, long-acting histamine antagonist, with selective peripheral H₁-receptor antagonist activity. Some of the metabolites (desloratadine and its hydroxylated metabolites) retain an antihistaminic activity and may partially contribute to the overall efficacy of the drug. This compound belongs to the class of organic compounds known as benzo-cyclo-hepta-pyridines. These are aromatic compounds containing a benzene ring and a pyridine ring fused to a seven membered carbocycle. In vitro studies with rupatadine at high concentration have shown an inhibition of the degranulation of mast cells induced by immunological and non-immunological stimuli as well in human mast cells and monocytes as the release of cytokines, particularly of the TNF. Rupatadine is a once-daily, non-sedating, selective and long acting drug with strong antagonist activity towards both histamine (H)₁ receptors and platelet-activating factor (PAF) receptors. 1,2 Rupatadine has dual antihistamine and PAF antagonist properties. It inhibits the degranulation of mast cells induced by immunological and non-immunological stimuli, and the release of cytokines, particularly tumour necrosis factor-alpha in human mast cells and monocytes. Although rupatadine shows high H₁ -receptor affinity, it has little or no activity on other central nervous system (CNS) receptors. Aiming to solve these problems, extended release floating drug delivery system for continuous delivery of RPTDN in the stomach was proposed [7]. Not only for reducing frequency of drug administration, but also it was suggested that prolonged gastric retention with slow continuous drug release, could result in the enhancement of RPTDN bioavailability, through reducing the expected drug precipitation from its acidic solution upon gastric emptying and its contact with higher pH environment in the intestine.

The aim of this work was to statistically optimize a novel, simple approach utilizing floating, gastro-retentive, controlled release lipid beads, potentially suitable for once daily administration aiming to improve the low and erratic bioavailability for poorly soluble basic drugs (using RPTDN as a model drug).

A 2⁴ full factorial design was utilized for the optimization of the effects of the lipid:drug ratio, % Pluronic F-127, % Sterotex, and ratio between Gelucire 43/01:Gelucire 50/13 on drug loading and release extent from the prepared beads. The pharmacokinetic parameters obtained from the optimized RPTDN lipid beads and Ralzin® as the marketed reference product were compared in healthy human volunteers.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Materials

Rupatadine (RPTDN) was supplied as a gift sample by Hetero Pharmaceuticals Ltd. (Cairo, Egypt), Gelucire 43/01 (hard fat, melting point 43 °C, HLB = 01) and Gelucire 50/13 (Stearoyl macrogol-32 glycerides, melting point 50 °C, HLB = 13) were kindly obtained as gift samples from Gattefosse (St Priest, Cedex, France), Sterotex NF (hydrogenated cotton seed oil, white solid powder, melting point 63 °C) was kindly supplied by Abitec Corp. (Janesville, WI), Pluronic F-127 (Ethylene Oxide/Propylene Oxide Block Copolymer, melting point 56 °C, HLB = 22) was provided by BASF (Ludwigshafen, Germany), and Hydrochloric acid (HCl) is of analytical reagent grade.

2.2. Preparation of Rupatadine floating lipid beads

Floating lipid RPTDN beads were prepared according to the method of Siepmann [10]. Briefly, the lipids were molten at 65 °C, mixed well and then RPTDN was dispersed. The molten dispersion containing the drug was then added to 100 ml pre-chilled water (4 °C) at a rate of 5 ml/min via 23 gauge syringe and stirred at 100 rpm on a magnetic stirrer (model SP 72220-26, Barnstead/Thermolyne, USA). Finally, the formed beads were filtered through Whatmann 41, collected, and stored in glass vials.

2.3. Formulation of Rupatadine floating lipid beads using 2⁴ full-factorial designs

A full factorial design (2⁴) was employed in the formulation of RPTDN floating lipid beads for the screening of the influence, and optimization of the four studied factors namely: Lipid (Gelucire 43/01, Gelucire 50/13 and Sterotex):drug ratio (A), percent of Pluronic F-127 (calculated using the total weight of beads including the drug) (B), percent of Sterotex (calculated from the lipid content) (C), and Gelucire 43/01:Gelucire 50/13 ratio (ratio in the remaining lipid content after calculating the amount of Sterotex) (D), each at two levels, as shown in Table 4.1. The observed responses were the percent of drug released after 1, 5, and 8 h (Y₁, Y₂, and Y₃, respectively) in

addition to the percent of drug loaded in the beads (Y_4) using Minitab® software (version 16.1.1). Sixteen formulae were suggested and randomly arranged by the software and duplicate

experimentation was carried out. The results of the observed responses were presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

Table-1: 2⁴ full factorial design layout: factors and responses.

Factors (independent variables)	Level used	
	-1	+1
A: Lipid:drug ratio	2:1	6:1
B: % Pluronic	6%	12%
C: % Sterotex	0%	2%
D: Gelucire 43/01:Gelucire 50/13 ratio	5:1	8:1
Responses (dependent variables)	Constraints	
Y_1 : Release (%) after 1 h	$7\% \leq Y_1 \leq 27\%$, target = 17%	
Y_2 : Release (%) after 5 h	$32\% \leq Y_2 \leq 52\%$, target = 42%	
Y_3 : Release (%) after 8 h	$57\% \leq Y_3 \leq 77\%$, target = 67%	
Y_4 : Loading efficiency (%)	$80\% \leq Y_4 \leq 100\%$, maximize	

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Floating behavior

All formulations exhibited immediate floating with no lag time in 0.1 N HCl 0.02% Tween 20 and floating was maintained up to 24 h, in contrast to most conventional floating systems (including gas-generating ones). This reflects the excellent floating ability of the prepared beads. The surface hydrophobicity imparted to the drug particles by the hydrophobic lipid coat, as well as the density of the investigated lipids (density of Gelucire 43/01, the major component, is 0.0856 g/cm^3) was responsible for this distinctive floating behavior. Similar results were reported by Shimpi *et al.* [13].

3.2. Analysis of the factorial design

The application of factorial design in pharmaceutical formulation development has played a key role in understanding the relationship between the independent variables and the responses to them. This helps the process of optimization by providing an empirical model equation for the response as a

function of the different variables. The experiment runs with independent variables and the observed responses for the 16 formulations are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 3. It was observed that RPTDN release profiles differed with changing the compositions of the prepared formulations. Some formulations showed initial burst release (reaching 68.87% in the first hour). Other formulations exhibited slow initial release. It is worthy to mention that the development of RPTDN gastroretentive sustained release dosage form could be considered as a challenge because of the high solubility of RPTDN in acidic media.

Figure-1: *In-vitro* dissolution profiles of RPTDN from the 16 formulae suggested by the factorial design.

Table-3: The composition of the prepared formulations in actual values (uncoded units) and their observed responses.

	Factors				Responses ^a			
	A	B	C	D	Y ₁	Y ₂	Y ₃	Y ₄
1	2	6	0	5	57.16 ± 11.36	81.09 ± 1.73	95.82 ± 2.01	79.10 ± 3.25
2	6	6	0	5	44.07 ± 4.85	74.02 ± 2.67	78.99 ± 2.22	91.80 ± 1.13
3	2	12	0	5	68.87 ± 11.57	93.41 ± 1.91	97.29 ± 0.39	93.50 ± 0.71
4	6	12	0	5	46.32 ± 9.81	72.20 ± 2.30	92.13 ± 3.03	95.50 ± 1.56
5	2	6	2	5	33.91 ± 2.10	66.34 ± 0.69	74.98 ± 0.43	88.50 ± 6.36
6	6	6	2	5	22.09 ± 9.04	36.17 ± 2.35	59.96 ± 2.32	83.30 ± 7.78
7	2	12	2	5	43.89 ± 13.86	78.20 ± 2.38	85.63 ± 2.73	90.40 ± 5.66
8	6	12	2	5	32.12 ± 2.42	68.60 ± 2.56	78.54 ± 0.22	78.90 ± 1.56
9	2	6	0	8	60.01 ± 2.82	81.38 ± 0.78	85.64 ± 0.36	80.10 ± 1.27
10	6	6	0	8	42.50 ± 2.86	63.81 ± 0.51	74.46 ± 0.79	97.60 ± 3.11
11	2	12	0	8	60.25 ± 5.96	83.45 ± 0.66	94.87 ± 0.10	93.50 ± 0.42
12	6	12	0	8	45.05 ± 7.64	71.81 ± 3.15	86.32 ± 1.68	98.10 ± 1.27
13	2	6	2	8	36.12 ± 0.21	64.43 ± 0.77	71.48 ± 0.83	94.60 ± 5.09
14	6	6	2	8	26.71 ± 8.03	40.00 ± 2.00	47.52 ± 0.60	82.00 ± 8.49
15	2	12	2	8	44.22 ± 8.08	72.56 ± 1.38	80.54 ± 1.94	95.80 ± 0.57
16	6	12	2	8	47.99 ± 13.76	66.44 ± 1.03	72.76 ± 0.38	91.40 ± 0.28

a- Mean ± standard deviation ($n = 2$).

Figure-2 represents normal probability plots of the effects of different formulation variables on the studied responses. The effects that lie along the normal probability line as round points are negligible (i.e. non-significant), whereas significant effects are those square points far from the normal probability line, i.e. not explained by natural experimental variation. The closer the point to the line the lower was its significance on the response. The plot can be divided into two regions. The region lies on the right (or positive) side of the line, where the factors and their interactions presented positive coefficients and the region on the left (or negative) side of the line, where the factors and their interaction presented negative coefficients [16].

The percent of drug released at different time intervals (Y_1 , Y_2 , and Y_3) (1, 5, and 8 h respectively) was synergistically affected by the percent of Pluronic F-127 (B). This might be attributed to its surface activity properties [17, 18] resulting in improvement of RPTDN solubility. Enhancement of

drug release could be also due to the pore formation ability of the surfactant [19]. In contrast, lipid:drug ratio (A) together with percent of Sterotex (C) had an antagonistic effect on RPTDN release. Lipids have the ability to retard drug release as a result of the increase in the lipid matrix density and the subsequent increase in the diffusion path length through which the drug molecules have to transverse. Also, on increasing the ratio of Gelucire 43/01:Gelucire 50/13 (D), a negative effect was observed, this could be due to the higher lipophilic nature of Gelucire 43/01 (HLB = 1) compared to Gelucire 50/13 with its surface activity properties (HLB = 13).

The relationship between the dependent and independent variables was further elucidated using three dimensional surface plots as shown in Fig.3. It could be concluded that the composition of the studied beads can be tailored in order to achieve the desired release profile of RPTDN.

Figure-2: Normal plot for screening of the influences and the significances of the studied factors.

Figure-3: Response surface plot showing the effect of different factors on the release profile of RPTDN from the studied lipid beads.

Regarding the loading efficiency, the percent of Pluronic F-127 (B) exhibited positive effect. Furthermore, it was clear that increasing Gelucire 43/01: Gelucire 50/13 ratio (D) increased the percent of drug entrapped. Finally, the percent of Sterotex (C) was observed to have a negative effect on the percent of drug loaded into the beads. The relationship between the dependent and independent variables was further elucidated using two dimensional contour plots as shown in Fig.4.4.

Figure-4: The relationship between the dependent and independent variables using two dimensional contour plots

3.3. Optimization

The linear regression models of the studied responses in terms of coded factors are represented in Table 4. The equations were left in their complete form without omitting any terms, to avoid loss of any important information [20]. After generating the polynomial equations relating the dependent and independent variables, the optimum formula was automatically generated by the software based on the desirability function aiming to attain zero order release profile of RPTDN over 12 h with initial target release of 17% in the first hour to act as loading dose as well as the highest loading efficiency. The constraints used in the optimization process were listed in Table-1.

Table-4: Coefficient estimates of the fitted regression model in terms of coded factors for the responses and the corresponding R^2 -values.

Response	Equation
Y_1 (% drug released after 1 h)	$Y_1 = 44.45 - 6.10A + 4.13B - 8.57C + 0.90D + 0.38AB + 2.44AC + 1.31AD + 2.04BC - 0.11BD + 1.98CD + 1.27ABC + 1.56ABD + 0.94ACD + 1.28BCD + 0.086ABCD$ ($R^2 = 0.8153$)
Y_2 (% drug released after 5 h)	$Y_2 = 69.62 - 7.99A + 6.21B - 8.03C - 1.64D + 1.92AB - 0.80AC + 0.52AD + 3.64BC - 0.63BD + 0.90CD + 2.94ABC + 1.11ABD + 0.64ACD - 0.58BCD - 1.40ABCD$ ($R^2 = 0.9964$)
Y_3 (% drug released after 8 h)	$Y_3 = 79.80 - 5.97A + 6.20B - 8.03C - 3.11D + 2.40AB - 0.76AC - 0.46AD + 1.74BC + 0.72BD - 0.24CD + 0.61ABC - 0.050ABD - 0.74ACD - 0.089BCD + 1.08ABCD$ ($R^2 = 0.9709$)
Y_4 (% loading efficiency)	$Y_4 = 89.63 + 0.19A + 2.51B - 1.52C - 2.01D - 1.36AB - 4.41AC + 0.44AD - 1.49BC + 0.56BD + 0.83CD + 1.59ABC + 0.77ABD - 0.48ACD - 1.08BCD + 1.04ABCD$ ($R^2 = 0.8401$)

Table-5: The observed and predicted values for the optimized formulation.

Factor	Optimized level		
A: Lipid:drug ratio	5.23		
B: % Pluronic	6		
C: % Sterotex	2		
D: Gelc 43/01:Gelc 50/13 ratio	5		
Response	Expected	Observed	Residual ^a
Y_1 : Release (%) after 1 h	24.38	15.38	9.00
Y_2 : Release (%) after 5 h	42.00	42.66	-0.66
Y_3 : Release (%) after 8 h	62.85	72.08	-9.23
Y_4 : Loading efficiency (%)	84.30	82.43	1.87
	a-Residual = expected	value - observed	value.

To examine the validity of the optimization process, a new batch of the optimized formula according to the computer levels was prepared and evaluated. As shown in [Table 5](#), a small residual between the observed and expected values of the studied responses was obtained. [Fig.5](#) demonstrates that the optimized formulation exhibited a release profile which was close to that of the suggested target release profile. Accordingly, these results validate the reliability of the optimization procedure.

Figure-5: Release profile of RPTDN from the optimized formula compared to target release profile.

3.4. Morphological examination and scanning electron microscope (SEM)

As shown in [Fig. 6](#), the optimized formula beads were spherical, showing a smooth surface. SEM micrographs of RPTDN-lipid beads are shown in [Fig.7](#) at different magnification powers before and after drug release. Initially before release, the beads were nearly spherical, with quite smooth surface without any pores or cracks ([Fig. 7a, 7c and 7e](#)). After eight hours of release study in 0.1 N HCl, cracks ([Fig. 7b](#)) and pores ([Fig. 6d and 6f](#)) were

observed on the surface of the beads (indicated by red arrows). This could be due to dissolution of Pluronic F-127 (the only soluble excipient) and this might possibly explain the observed positive effect of Pluronic F-127 on RPTDN release mentioned earlier [[19](#)].

Figure-6: Light photograph for the optimized formula.

3.5. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) provides information about melting, crystallization, decomposition and physicochemical status of the drug as well as its interaction with different excipients [[21](#)]. Pure RPTDN exhibited a single sharp endothermic peak at 121 °C corresponding to its melting point [[22](#)]. Sterotex showed a single sharp endothermic peak at 60 °C and Pluronic F-127 showed sharp endothermic peak at 55.5 °C, corresponding to their melting points. For Gelucire 43/01 and Gelucire 50/13, each showed single endothermic peak at 39.7 °C and 41.6 °C respectively corresponding to their melting points. The endothermic peak of the drug was shifted to a lower temperature in the optimized formula and in all drug-excipient mixtures (1:1 w/w) except in case of Gelucire 50/13, where the peak of the drug was not further observed.

Figure-7: Scanning electron microscope of optimized RPTDN lipid beads. (a) Before release at magnification 50×, (b) after 8 h release in 0.1 N HCl at magnification 50×. (c) Before release at magnification 500×, (d) after 8 h release in 0.1 N HCl at magnification 500×, (e) before release at magnification 1000×, (f) after 8 h release in 0.1 N HCl at magnification 1000×.

In case of Gelucire 50/13, the complete disappearance of the endothermic peak corresponding to the melting RPTDN, might be due to RPTDN complete solubility in the fused Gelucire 50/13 before reaching its melting point during the DSC scan. In the other thermograms, the presence of RPTDN shifted endothermic peak, indicates the partial solubility of RPTDN in the melted excipients and that some RPTDN crystals still exist upon reaching the melting point of RPTDN in the DSC scan [23].

It was worthy to note that the difference in thermal behavior of RPTDN observed with both Gelucire 50/13 and Gelucire 43/01 might be due to the different chemical structure of the studied Gelucires where, Gelucire 43/01 is a hard fat and Gelucire 50/13 is Stearoyl macrogol-32 glycerides.

3.6. X-ray diffraction (XRD):

As shown in Fig.8, pure RPTDN is highly crystalline as indicated by the numerous sharp characteristic peaks at angles of 2θ at 10.29, 20.79, 20.955, and 24.56. The existence of these peaks in diffractograms of the studied physical mixtures with the excipients and the optimized formula indicates that RPTDN maintained its crystalline

state during mixing with the studied excipients and preparation of the optimized formula.

4.3.7. In-vivo study

Mean plasma concentrations of RPTDN-time profile achieved after single administration of both the optimized RPTDN-lipid beads equivalent to 25 mg RPTDN and Ralzin® 25 mg are shown in Fig.9. The mean pharmacokinetic parameters were shown for both formulae in Table 6. Statistical analysis showed that there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the values of T_{max} , AUC_{0-24} , and $AUC_{0-\infty}$ of the optimized RPTDN-loaded lipid beads compared to Ralzin® tablets while statistical insignificant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed in case of C_{max} .

Figure-8: XRD diffractograms of RPTDN, Sterotex NF, Pluronic F-127, Gelucire 43/01, Gelucire 50/13, physical mixtures (1:1) and optimized formula.

Figure-9: Plasma concentration–time curve of Ralzin® tablets, and Optimized RPTDN-lipid beads.

Table-6: Mean pharmacokinetic parameters \pm standard deviation of Ralzin® tablets, and optimized RPTDN-lipid beads.

PK parameter	Ralzin® tablets	Optimized RPTDN-lipid beads
C_{max} (ng/ml)	41.3375 ± 5.57	82.7387 ± 17.30
T_{max} (h)	3 ± 0.35	$7 \pm 1.41^*$
AUC_{0-24} (ng h/ml)	292.348 ± 94.4	$1233.37 \pm 211.32^*$
$AUC_{0-\infty}$ (ng h/ml)	307.19 ± 68.9	$1856.86 \pm 301.3^*$

*Statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean AUC_{0-24} and the $AUC_{0-\infty}$ of the optimized RPTDN-loaded lipid beads were found to be 4.23 times, and 6.04 times that of Ralzin® tablets respectively. The delayed T_{max} , increased C_{max} and higher AUC indicate a slow and prolonged absorption of RPTDN from the optimized RPTDN loaded lipid beads formula with higher bioavailability and more extended plasma concentration–time profile over 24 h in comparison with the commercially available Ralzin® tablets. This could be due to the increased gastric residence of RPTDN beads as well as the gradual release of RPTDN in its acidic medium. Also, it could be suggested that the incorporation of Pluronic F-127 and Gelucire 50/13, which are reported for the bioavailability enhancing effect [24,25], contributed to the improvement of RPTDN bioavailability.

4.CONCLUSION:

Promising, novel as well as simple optimized floating gastro retentive RPTDN lipid beads were

successfully developed. The beads were characterized by: excellent floating behavior, zero order release profile for 12 h, high entrapment efficiency, and potentially suitable for once daily administration. The suggested floating lipid beads could be easily tailored by changing their composition to achieve the desired drug release profile, thereby considered an effective approach in developing extended release formulations for poorly soluble basic drugs with improved bioavailability.

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